

Review

The Update in the Treatments of Surgical Wound Healing: An Overview

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Abstract: Surgical wound healing is an intricate and complex biological process influenced by various factors. The advent of novel technologies and therapeutic approaches has revolutionized the management of surgical wounds, leading to improved outcomes and reduced morbidity. This review paper aims to study the recent advancements in the treatment of surgical wound healing. The fundamental stages of wound healing, including hemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and remodeling, highlighting the underlying cellular and molecular mechanisms involved. Traditional methods that were used for wound care are sutures, staples, and adhesive agents. Subsequently, the review delves into the emerging techniques and therapies that have shown promising results in promoting surgical wound healing. These include the use of advanced dressings, such as hydrogels, foams, and films, which provide an optimal wound environment for tissue regeneration. Additionally, the application of growth factors, such as platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF) and epidermal growth factor (EGF), and stem cell therapies have demonstrated their potential in accelerating wound closure and enhancing tissue regeneration. Furthermore, role of bioengineered skin substitutes, hyperbaric oxygen therapy, low level laser therapy and negative pressure wound therapy in the management of complex wounds. These innovative approaches have paved the way for personalized wound care and wound repair and regeneration. The paper also addresses the importance of infection control in surgical wound healing and highlights the advancements in antimicrobial strategies, including the use of antibacterial agents, nanoparticles, and photodynamic therapy. This comprehensive study provides a valuable update on the evolving landscape of treatments for surgical wound healing. By highlighting the recent advancements and novel therapeutic approaches, it aims to guide healthcare professionals in making informed decisions regarding the management of surgical wounds, ultimately improving patient outcomes and quality of life.

Keywords: PDGF, EGF, Hyperbaric oxygen therapy, Photodynamic therapy

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Introduction

In everyday pathology, surgical wounds and skin injuries have been a difficult problem with frequent mortality and morbidity, due to both pre-operative and post-operative infection and wound complications [1]. As skin is the first line of defense and it protects us against the microbial invasion as well as external environment. Any skin injury and tissue

loss results in the entrance of microbes into the human body, which could cause an infection. Severe skin damage leads to the loss of body fluids, nutrients and electrolytes that is a life threatening situation [2].

Skin regeneration and healing is an intricate process that involves highly complicated sequences of cellular and molecular pathways that are activated in response to wound and proceed in a planned, orderly manner to heal the damaged and injured tissues. Simple wounds are any alterations or injuries to the anatomical functions or structures brought on by significant organ breakage, such as those of the skin. Other structures, such as muscles, tendons, nerves, blood vessels, and bone, may also be affected by the damage. In general, wounds are categorized as either acute or chronic [3]. While surgical wounds are shallow, superficial or deep wounds on the skin or mucous membranes caused by a surgical procedure in which the skin, mucosa, and underlying tissue are cut with a scalpel. Surgical wounds are easily approximated spontaneously or using Mio sutures as these wound have clean margins [4].

Classification of Surgical Wounds	
Clean	Primary closed, not emergency, non-traumatic, no acute inflammation;
Clean-Contaminated	Urgent or emergency; elective opening of respiratory, gastrointestinal, biliary or genitourinary;
Contaminated	Non-infected inflammation; discharge from gastrointestinal tract;
Dirty	Infected inflammation, like an swelling, eruption and abscess;

Wound injuries result in suffering, pain, bleeding, impairment, and even death. Surgery-related wound infections cause frequent and dangerous consequences. Infections at surgical sites can extend hospital stays by 5 to 20 days and significantly raise expenses. The crucial period for the development of wound infections is the first few hours after tissue has been infected by bacteria. Therefore, even though infections are frequently not discovered until a few days following surgery, perioperative factors affect the frequency of infections [5].

As long as there has been mankind, wounds have always been frequent and prevailing and the risks and hazards accompanying with their treatment. Wound is examined easily if symptoms of wound are clear. However, all the processes taking place in the wound occurrence and its healing and the factors influencing them have been studied for last two decades. For the last four or five eras, the history of surgery is considered the history of wound therapy. Treatment for wounds has always aimed to minimize complications and hazards caused by the wound itself such as Pain, hemorrhage, loss of skin continuity and tissue substance in a wound have tested man's ingenuity throughout the ages [6].

Depending on the hospital, clinician, and healthcare staff, there are various wound types, and the treatment and management approaches are diverse according to the type of wounds. Costs associated with wound care and management include hospitalization (greater than 50%), nursing time (30%–35%), and supplies and dressings (15%–20%) [2]. Various treatment procedures and alternatives are accessible in the field of wound care as there have specialists who expert in managing and treating wounds. A steady stream of new products, modalities and technology is an addition to the wound care field, even though many surgeons depend on "tried and true" therapies and achieve good outcomes with this. Negative pressure wound devices, laser therapies and oxygen hyperbaric therapies are a reasonably recent development in wound care, and their indications are constantly being expanded to include wound management aspects for which there were previously few alternatives.

Innovative wound-dressing products can change the environment around the wound to improve healing conditions. The development of bio-synthetics and tissue engineering has led to the development of skin substitutes and cell therapies that not only offer unique, efficient temporary wound coverage but are also altering the way wounds are managed. Growth factors and biologic substances can be used to support the wound and aid in accelerating or modifying the healing process [7]. This study aim to critically examining the recent developments in therapeutic and

clinical techniques and modalities for surgical wound healing and educate the public and offer clinical guidance. In addition, there has been a lot of work done to understand the pathophysiology of healing, with a focus on innovative therapeutic strategies and the ongoing development of technology for both acute and chronic wounds.

Pathologic wound healing: By definition, surgical wounds are initially acute and the majority of them heal normally without impairment or consequences. However, issues like infection and wound dehiscence (opening) could arise and cause either a delay in healing or a breakdown of the wound, or even both. Physiological, deficient, exuberant, and regenerative are the possible responses to skin injury. A typical physiological response to injury results in wound healing and the production of scars, while abnormal reactions can either result in inadequate or excessive healing. Deficient healing results from insufficient matrix component deposition or re-epithelialization, which prolongs and impairs the healing process. Chronic wounds are frequently caused by a lack of structural integrity and regenerative capacity. Generally, subcutaneous tissue loss, failure to re-epithelialize, and a necrosis-infection combination are examples of clinical symptoms. Excessive neutrophil infiltration has a major impact on skin regeneration and wound healing. Growth factors and connective tissue are both destroyed by neutrophil-secreted collagenases (such MMP-8) and elastases, respectively. Deficient wound healing can be caused by excessive use of exogenous corticosteroids, starvation, exposed to radioactivity, infection, and systemic disease. While excessive healing occurred in a result of collagen deposition in the dermis that leads to hypertrophic scars or keloids [8].

Phases of wound healing:

The healing and restoration of damaged skin is a complex process due to its critical role in keeping the body in hemostatic state. However, it is a very complicated because it depends on several cell types and metabolic pathways. It is a highly organized process that is susceptible to both endogenous and exogenous components. This biological process is divided into four phases; Haemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and remodeling phase.

Haemostatic Phase: The immune system and inflammatory pathways are involved by the coagulation cascade in order to stop blood and fluid losses, eliminate necrotic tissue, and prevent infection. In order to create the blood clot, platelet aggregation is induced by activators like collagen and various tissue factor. These activators cause the discharge of chemotactic factors as well as growth factors.

Inflammatory Phase: This stage begins a few minutes after skin injury. Increased levels of histamine and inflammatory cytokines causes edema and redness as a result of high blood flow and vascular permeability, which encourages the neutrophils infiltration, lymphocytes, and monocytes and macrophages to the injury site. Killing of bacteria by phagocytosis and the formation of free radicals are required to control infection and eliminate necrotic tissue respectively [9]. The removal of apoptotic neutrophils and other dead cells is another function of macrophages. They also secrete cytokines and growth factors that promote angiogenesis [10]. Lymphocytes often produce a specialized response against microorganisms for 72 hours.

Proliferation Phase: The proliferative phase generally begins two days after the skin tissue injury, coexists with the inflammatory stage. Fibroplasia is characterized by the movement and proliferation of fibroblasts and endothelial cells to the wound site, which leads to the secretion of the cytokines and growth factors [11]. Fibroblasts play a crucial role in this stage. Additionally, these cells support keratinocyte migration and angiogenesis, both of which are critical steps in the re-epithelialization process. This makes it possible for granulation tissue, which is made up of fibroblasts, macrophages, fibronectin, glycoprotein, and hyaluronic acid, to progressively replace the prior fibrin matrix. In the later parts of this phase, macrophages stimulate some fibroblasts that have been drawn from the bone marrow or the edge of the wound and can differentiate into myofibroblasts. These last cells, which are only present in adult wounds and

release alpha-smooth muscle actin and elastic fibers, play a significant role in the process of wound contraction. This stage often lasts for three weeks.

Remodeling Phase: The final phase, known as remodeling or maturation, lasts the longest up to a year or more. The initial processes that were engaged after skin damage are less active and cease during this phase. The apoptosis of myofibroblasts and macrophages is occurred while the neovasculature is deteriorating. Both wound contraction and collagen remodeling characterize the maturation stage. Myofibroblast activity results in a steady rise in the tensile strength of wounds throughout remodeling, despite the fact that the tissue never recovers the characteristics of intact skin. Collagen remodeling is accomplished by maintaining the balance that is regulated by the activity of the matrix metalloproteinases [12].

Wound assessment: Surgical wounds are often clean and created on healthy tissue in comparison to chronic wounds so their recovery is frequently unaffected by underlying diseases, pathologies and a high bacterial burden. These condition may influence the chronic wounds and impair the healing process [4]. Both invasive and non-invasive technologies can be used to evaluate and categorize wound extent. The perimeter of the wound, its surface area, volume, the degree of weakening, and the tissue viability can all be assessed non-invasively [13]. Various characteristics including Blood flow, infection, edema, swelling, redness, recurrent trauma, innervation, wound metabolism, past injury handling can be used to describe a wound. All these features can be studied as an evidence of origin, condition and pathophysiology of a wound. In the end, it is important to evaluate wounds in relation to the host since patient status is crucial in determining how systemic elements will affect the wound. Since the healing process is dynamic, methodical, and consistent evaluation, including a continuous evaluation of wound extent, type, and severity, it can be difficult to assess the healing process. Persistent wounds reduce quality of life, and may be fatal even cause mortality. Wounds have been referred to as a "Silent Epidemic" for these reasons [14].

Wound complications: Surgery-related wounds typically heal by primary closure, a process in which the wound edges are pulled together and placed next to one another. According to Coulthard (2010), sutures (stitches), staples, sticky tape, or glue are frequently used to help wounds close, and healing normally starts soon after. Surgical wounds in different patients have different symptoms and features, such as over age or medical conditions like malnutrition, uncontrolled diabetes, circulatory and cardiac issues, poor immunity, and obesity, making the wounds difficult to heal and caused many wound complications i.e., Dehiscence and SSI (surgical site infection) [15].

Wound dehiscence: The crucial sign of wound healing is the healing ridge, which is a stiffness or induration beneath the incision line. The growth of new tissue beneath the incision can be felt after 5-9 days following surgery. At this stage, the absence of the healing ridge can signal the impending occurrence of dehiscence, or wound rupture. When the two opposite sides of the wound are unable to effectively 'knit' together, dehiscence results in the wound falling open. Dehiscence, or the separation of the edges of the wound, can potentially prevent a wound from healing. Technical causes of dehiscence include knots slipping, sutures ripping through tissue, and insufficient splinting and patient-related factors that include wound infection and obesity [16].

If there is a wound infection, dehiscence is more likely to happen. Nutritional depletion also hinders the healing of wounds. For instance, a protein deficit might result in decreased wound tensile strength and a higher likelihood of dehiscence. Malnourished patients are more likely to develop wound infections because they lack the energy sources needed for cellular repair and strong immunity [17].

Some other factors like glucocorticoid or corticosteroid use, and diabetes mellitus are known to impede healing, susceptible to dehiscence. According to [18], diabetes weakens the inflammatory response, impairing the immune system and raising the risk of infection. Additionally, collagen synthesis and deposition are decreased, which affects

wound healing and strength. Another risk factor is mechanical stress, which can be coughing, or being obese, all of which impose unnecessary strain on the wound site.

Surgical site infection: The Department of Health (2005) defines surgical site infection as an infection associated with a surgical operation that influence the wound or deeper tissues touched and handled during the process. With a documented frequency of at least 10%, SSIs are one of the four main categories of healthcare-associated infections, and they are recognized to be a serious issue for patients. Patients who have SSI may experience greater pain, frequent dressing changes, limited mobility, and extended hospital stays. For effective SSI care, early infection signals detection is crucial. The three outcomes that can result from wounds acquiring microbial species are contamination, colonization, and infection.

Contamination: If appropriate nutritional and physical circumstances exist, microorganisms can grow in any wound this situation is known as contamination. Colonization: Microbial species multiply and develop, but they do not harm the host or start a wound infection. Infection: Cellular damage and overt host immunological responses result from microbial proliferation, multiplication, and invasion into host tissue during an infection. Various studied showed that application of a topical antibiotic could stop the growth of wound infection if the point of transition to overt infection can be correctly detected. However, this result has not yet been determined with certainty [4].

Wound care: Wound care Using the TIME Principle; Tissue (T), Infection (I), Moisture (M), and Epithelial (E) ("TIME") synthesizes all significant elements that adversely affect the healing process in the context of wound care. Since there is no precise and systematic technique to evaluate acute wounds, TIME principle can be studied as a useful manual for wound care [19]. Basic ideas that can be divided into four categories are described in the acronym TIME: tissues; Examining and removing any necrotic tissue, dressing material that is sticking to the wound, multi-organism detritus, or biofilm from the wound bed is known as debridement of tissue (T) [20]. Infection (I): evaluation of the etiology and care of the infection utilizing systemic or topically applied antibiotics. Moisture (M); Evaluation of the etiology and treatment of wound exudate under moisture balance, Epithelial edge advancement (E) Evaluation of the advancement of the edges and the condition of the surrounding skin in terms of epithelial edges [21].

Wound cleansing: Surgical wounds may need to be cleansed in addition to using the TIME principle for wound care and management and to remove blood or exudate from the surrounding skin. Although cleansing has been recognized as a critical contributory element in procedure-related wound discomfort. A quite care should be given on open wounds to remove wound debris, excess exudate, or dressing residues from the wound bed. By using sterile gauze swabs wet with saline will help to reduce pain and tissue trauma while cleansing the area around wound [4].

Therapeutics for wound healing: Wound management and handling required a complete assessment of the patients and wound itself to determine the appropriate measures which must be taken for favorable consequences. The most frequent therapeutic option for wound care is the use of wound dressings and debridement processes. But a variety of advanced wound-healing modalities, such as bioengineered skin and tissue equivalents, negative-pressure wound therapy (NPWT), hyperbaric oxygen (HBO) therapy, platelet therapy, and many others, have been developed as a result of the incorporation of technical advances with the understanding of the complex cellular and molecular pathways of wound healing.

Debridement: The removal of foreign objects, dead or injured tissue, and debris from a wound is known as debridement [22]. In order to create a clean wound bed, debridement of wounds involves any method that eliminates the contaminated tissue, cell debris, or dead, devitalized, fibrous material. According to O'Brien, debridement has set a basis for subsequent wound healing. A range of techniques, including surgery, biosurgical (larvae) debridement,

chemical debridement, autolytic debridement, mechanical debridement, and enzymatic debridement, may be used to remove tissue and cell debris [23].

Wound dressings: The frequent therapeutic option for wound healing is applying several types of wound dressings in accordance with the type, depth, location, and size of the wound. Generally, a wound dressing acts as a physical barrier between the wound and the external environment, preventing microbial growth and further injury and accelerating the healing process [24].

The invasion of microbes into the wound and their presence causes the wound healing process to be delayed and disrupted. In order to avoid wound infection and the development of bacterial biofilm, an ideal wound dressing should include antimicrobial qualities. An antibacterial wound dressing can stop bacteria and other microbe's invasion at injury site, promoting the natural healing process.

Classification of dressings: There are generally three types of wound dressings: 1) traditional i.e., the leaves of trees and plants, cobwebs and honey 2) passive i.e., sterile gauze, cotton pads, and bandage, and 3) modern wound dressings i.e., foams, films, hydrocolloids, and hydrogels [2].

Cell-Based Technologies: Autogenous and non-autogenous skin grafts, which are frequently used to treat skin ulcerations, may have a number of limitations, including the possibility of immune rejection, the transmission of infections, and the development of a donor site that may experience discomfort and pain, scarring, infection, and a delayed healing process. Growing living human tissues for transplants was created by the necessity for an easily accessible, non-antigenic tissue that shares many of the histologic and functional properties of healthy human skin. From the earliest auto-graft and allograft preparations through biosynthetic and tissue-engineered skin replacements and cell-based therapies, tissue engineering has entirely changed skin grafting. These cutting-edge treatments include cultured allogeneic and autologous keratinocyte grafts, in addition to autologous and allogeneic composites, and many more are in the process. The ones that are now accessible are allogeneic bi-layered cultured skin equivalent, human fibroblast-derived temporary skin substitute, and human fibroblast-derived dermal substitute and allogeneic bi-layered cultured skin [25].

Growth factors: For the improvement of healing process the topical administration of growth factors after debridement is a possible and most favorable strategy. Recombinant growth factors are among the approved pharmaceuticals that can be purchased as preparations for external use in the form of solutions, ointments, lotions, and gels. The high doses and frequent administration of growth factor-containing drugs are the current treatment over a long or short duration but it has serious adverse effects, including oncogenesis. Such high dosages of growth factors could raise the price of treatment. To ensure that growth factors are broadly accepted, concerns over the cost and safety of growth factor-loaded drug delivery systems in clinical stages should be discussed in details. However, several clinical investigations of growth factors used topically have provided reliable evidence of therapeutic results. But further investigation is needed that combine surgical interventions with cell substitutes and growth factors to promote wound healing [26].

Growth factors	Administration	Function
PDGF	Topical	Stimulation of cellular growth, chemo-attractant, neo-vascularization
VEGF	Topical	Angiogenic; propagation and differentiation of endothelial cells
EGF	Topical or intra-lesional injection	Stimulate differentiation of keratinocytes; increase tensile strength of new skin

bFGF	Topical	Stimulate proliferation, neo-vascularization
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Negative pressure wound therapy: Since the late 1990s, wounds have been treated with negative pressure wound therapy (NPWT). It is also referred as vacuum-assisted closure (VAC) or topical negative pressure therapy, is another innovative wound healing technique that enhances wound healing by applying differential suction or vacuum to the wounds. It is now frequently used to treat both acute and chronic wounds, including pressure wounds, trauma, infection, necrotizing fasciitis, infected wounds, and wounds from surgical incisions.

In order to avoid complications at the surgical site, negative pressure wound care is being extensively utilized on closed incisional wounds [27]. Despite the fact that NPWT devices come in a variety of shapes and sizes, the basic elements are the same. These devices essentially consist of four parts: 1. a porous material covering the wound site, 2. a drainage port is affixed over the porous material and is linked to vacuum pump, 3. a regulated vacuum pump, the vacuum pump applies pressures between 80 and 125 mmHg. 4. An adhesive dressing (made of polyurethane) that seal the wound. The porous substance is commonly polyurethane foam with pores that range in size from 400 to 600 μm , which seems ideal to promote uniform pressure distribution within the wound and maximize tissue regrowth.

Although the mechanism of action of NPWT is not fully understood, but it is believed it improves the wound healing by four main mechanisms including Macro-deformation, micro-deformation, wound fluid removal and edema decrease, and alterations of wound environment. According to experimental data, NPWT may promote further changes to the wound's microenvironment by boosting local blood flow and the development of granulation tissue and by lowering bacterial contamination, edema, and exudate. NPWT modifies the cytokine profile to be less inflammatory and wound healing is improved through alteration in the expression of multiple enzymes i.e., matrix metalloproteinases [15].

Despite the fact that NPWT has been shown to be beneficial in treating a variety of wounds, as was already noted, there may be some potential risks or consequences are associated when using it. Clinicians should therefore be familiar with methods for avoiding them. Three significant issues, including bleeding, infection, and retention of the foam dressing, have the potential to be fatal. Infection, necrotic tissue, or coagulopathy can exacerbate the mechanical injury to the underlying tissues, which is the main cause of bleeding. The risk of hemorrhage in the presence of exposed blood vessels is raised, hence it is recommended that foam dressing should not come into direct contact with exposed blood vessels, organ, nerves, or anastomotic sites. Regarding infections, there isn't a definite correlation between infection and NPWT use. So treatment of infections is necessary before using NPWT. Other issues include pain while dressing and a patient's allergy to the foam material or adhesive dressing that can also impair healing [12].

The NPWT regulates the exudate and protects against infection and cross-contamination by removing fluid. Additionally, this procedure lessens edema, accelerates angiogenesis, aids in preserving wound hydration, and ultimately speed up contraction of the wound borders. There have been some clinical trials, but they were not definitive, thus a multicenter, carefully planned clinical trial is required to confirm the NPWT's efficacy as a tool for wound healing. There are numerous likely mediators of NPWT's potential impact on wound healing in closed surgical incisions, many of which are not completely clear. However, the device has been made portable for usage in public spaces and community setting.

There are many commercially available NPWT devices right now. The two most popular systems are RENASYS® NPWT (Smith & Nephew, UK) and VAC® therapy (Kinetic Concepts Inc., USA). Both systems comprised of a portable pump that can deliver adjustable negative pressure. An emergent advancement has made in NPWT that is the addition of 'instillations' of sterile water, saline, antiseptics, or antibiotics. So new negative pressure wound therapy with instillation (NPWTi) systems are V.A.C. VeraFlo Therapy (KCI, San Antonio, Texas) [15].

Laser therapy: For the treatment of open wounds, lasers light amplification by stimulated emission of radiation (or laser) has been utilized in Europe and Russia for more than 35 years. Low-energy lasers that can increase tissue temperature

by 0.1°C to 0.5°C are used to treat wounds.¹⁹⁵ Biostimulation is the term used for low-energy laser therapy.¹⁹⁶ The Arndt-Schulz law, which states that "less is more," appears to govern how low-energy lasers work. In other words, weak bio-stimulation stimulates physiological activity, moderate bio-stimulation favours physiologic effect, strong bio-stimulation inhibits physiological processes, and very powerful bio-stimulation stops physiological stimulation and is harmful [28].

Wounded skin exhibits enhanced cellular activity in response to low-energy stimulation. It is unclear what causes the increased physiologic activity. Ascorbic acid uptake by cells is thought to be stimulated, as are photoreceptors in the mitochondrial respiratory chain, changes in cellular ATP or cyclic AMP levels, and cell membranes stabilization (Farivar et al., 2014). The helium-neon laser and gallium-arsenide (or infrared) lasers are the two most often utilized lasers in clinical settings. Ischemic, hypoxic, and infected wounds have been proven to heal more quickly after using lasers (particularly when paired with hyperbaric oxygen therapies) [29].

Low-level laser therapy: Low-level laser therapy uses a variety of gas components and is one of the phototherapeutic methods. Helium/neon, aluminum/gallium/indium/phosphide, and gallium/arsenide with various wavelengths are the most promising low-level laser therapies to target various depths of tissue. In addition to wavelength, essential Low-level laser therapy parameters include power, pulse rate, pulse duration, total irradiation time, intensity, and dose. This kind of laser works by producing photo-thermal effects, but Low-level laser therapy often does not result in significant temperature changes [30].

Although the precise mechanism of this procedure is unknown, it appears that this therapy lowers wound inflammation by limiting the amount of chemicals that cells make and by lowering pain and inflammation-related enzymes. The appropriate wavelength, radiation dose, treatment duration, and location are important variables in this approach. According to reports. Acute, chronic, and postoperative wounds can all benefit from Low-level laser therapy [31].

Platelet therapy: Megakaryocytes found in bone marrow are the main source of the blood's platelets. The main function of these cells are hemostasis, coagulation, inflammation, and wound healing. Alpha granules, a type of secretory organelle found in platelets, are capable of secreting cytokines, growth factors, and extracellular matrix modulators. These elements can speed up the healing of wounds by re-epithelialization, differentiation of mesenchymal cells, and fibroblast proliferation and activation, and connective tissue repair. In addition to the aforementioned, platelets also operate as a barrier against microorganisms by secreting chemokines, cytokines, and microbicide proteins such kinocidins. Depending on the number and concentration of platelets, different fractions of blood plasma are present for example Platelet-rich plasma (PRP) and Platelet-poor plasma (PPP).

Platelet-rich plasma (PRP) is a blood plasma that has a high concentration of platelets and growth factors, is often ten times higher than normal. Higher growth factor concentrations in platelet therapy speed up the healing of wounds. PRP has been used in clinical settings to treat both chronic and acute wounds. PRP generally promotes angiogenesis, collagen production, endothelial, epithelial, and epidermal regeneration, as well as tissue repair. In PRP, the degradation of platelet granules starts the production several growth factors, which speeds up the healing process. VEGF, which is a common component of PRP, is thought to be one of the most efficient growth factors for angiogenesis and is also in charge of producing other substances such as matrix metalloproteinases [32].

PRP plays a crucial role in wound healing, particularly during the homeostasis stage. Anti-inflammatory and pro-inflammatory cytokines are particular platelet components that may contribute to the activation of wound repair. PRP has many antibacterial properties that protect against wound infection [33]. Numerous studies have revealed that PRP has antibacterial activity against certain bacteria, such as *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, but not against *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), and *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*). In general, employing PRP can shorten the length of treatment and be a safe and affordable way for healing various wounds.

Over the past 20 years platelet-rich concentrates (PRC) have also been taken into consideration in a number of medical sectors due to its regenerative properties. The second generation of PRCs, known as Plasma-rich fibrin, is created by simply centrifuging blood in a tube. PRF is used as an autologous biological supplement with long-term growth factor release. It is possible for PRF to release a number of growth factors, including PDGF, IGF, TGF-, and VEGF, which are highly effective in angiogenesis and speed up the healing of wounds [34]. Additionally, Platelet-rich fibrin has the right quantity of thrombin, which encourages the migration of fibroblasts and endothelial cells and improves angiogenesis. Some benefits of employing Platelet-rich fibrin include minimal cost, no immune response stimulation, accelerated tissue regeneration, and simple, one-step preparation. Platelet-rich plasma has a high concentration of growth factors, which speeds up the healing of wounds. However, it has been found that Platelet-rich fibrin heals more quickly than Platelet-rich plasma (Mirhaj et al., 2022). Numerous facilities and advanced autologous PRP systems such as plasma rich in growth factors (PRGF-system), platelet concentrates collection system (PCCS-kit), gravitational platelet separation (GPS system), plateltex and smart PReP system have been espousing for the treatment of wound [32].

Oxygen Therapy: In both surgical and chronic wound healing, the availability of oxygen is crucial. The oxygen therapy treatment approach relies on administration of 100% pure oxygen in a completely closed chamber at a pressure of about three times that of atmospheric pressure. This therapy has been associated with numerous positive physiological effects, including improved collagen deposition, increased angiogenesis, activated leukocytes, and decreased edema.

Hyperbaric oxygen therapy and topical hyperbaric oxygen therapy were the two main oxygen-based therapies utilized to treat wounds for a very long time. Another distinct type of oxygen generation and delivery wound care devices that continuously treat wounds with oxygen has just come into existence. These are also known as transdermal oxygen therapy or continuous diffusion of oxygen therapy. There are some technological and clinical distinctions among the three approaches, even though they all use oxygen to aid wound healing.

Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy is a procedure in which a patient uses a therapy chamber to breathe 100% oxygen at a pressure greater than that of the surrounding air, or higher than 1 atmosphere absolute [35]. Improved neovascularization, ECM production, and reduced inflammation are among the advantages of HBOT [36]. Neovascularization happens simultaneously by these two mechanisms. First of all, HBOT increases the local production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species, which in turn stimulates the synthesis of certain growth factors like VEGF, TGF-beta, and angiopoietin. Second, it promotes vasculogenesis, the process by which circulating stem/progenitor cells from the bone marrow are recruited and differentiated to produce vessels. This is because the bone marrow produces more nitric oxide (NO), which mobilizes SPCs in healthy people, diabetics, and people who have had radiation exposure in the past. Additionally, hyperbaric oxygen therapy promotes the creation of the extra cellular matrix which leads to a fast recovery.

Topical Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy THOT, which is developed from hyperbaric oxygen therapy, surrounds the wounded area with a chamber that is firmly sealed to avoid leaks and is then loaded with oxygen from an external source at pressures just a little higher than atmospheric values but at high flow rates. This enables a wound surface environment that is rich in oxygen. In comparison both therapies has benefits such as a lower risk profile for a variety of therapeutic patient populations by avoiding oxygen toxicity, in addition to being able to be used in a wider range of settings at a lower cost and in a more practical manner [37].

But ECM formation is not entirely optimized in hyperbaric oxygen therapy, which causes a slower rate of wound closure. While topical hyperbaric oxygen therapy has been demonstrated to speed up the healing of chronic wounds and optimizing the ECM formation. Numobag® (Numotech, USA), is an example of topical hyperbaric oxygen therapy

device [38]. It is considered that topical hyperbaric oxygen therapy may be suitable as adjuvant for chronic and painful wound healing.

Bacterial biofilms in wounds: Recently, more attention has been paid to how bacteria biofilms affect the speed of wound healing. Biofilms are intricate formations that are permanently affixed to a biological or non-biological surface and comprise microbial related cells embedded in an extracellular matrix of hydrated extra-polymeric substances. While only 6% of acute wounds have biofilms present, the incidence of biofilms in chronic wounds is 10 times higher (60%). This mechanism may explain why infections caused by *Staphylococcus aureus* or *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* frequently fail to heal in the presence of foreign bodies like sutures, implants, and vascular conduits until the foreign body is removed. The foreign object serves as a surface for bacterial growth, and the biofilm blocks the action of antimicrobials. Because of the biofilms that *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* form, it is reasonable to suppose that many chronic wounds do not heal. Future studies may shed light on the significance of biofilms in the healing of acute and persistent, troublesome wounds [39].

Antibiotics and antiseptics: There are two basic ways to treat surgical wound healing by secondary intention that are considered clinically suitable i.e., use of antibiotics either topical (by applying an antibiotic or antiseptic), or systemically (by administering an antibiotic orally, intravenously, or intramuscularly). Topical medicines only target a certain area of the body, but systemic antibiotics affect the entire body. Antibiotics are chemicals that either kill or stop the development of microorganisms. Groups of medications with comparable mechanisms of action, such as penicillins, cephalosporins, aminoglycosides, macrolides, and quinolones, are used as systemic antibiotic treatments while clindamycin, metronidazole, trimethoprim, and co-trimazole are additional antibiotics that do not fall within one of these major categories. Antibiotics and antiseptics are both examples of topical antimicrobial agents. Topical treatments can be divided into two categories: those that have a brief contact time with the wound (unless used as a pack or soak) such as lotions used for wound irrigation or cleaning, or both, and those that have a prolonged contact time like creams, ointments, and impregnated dressings. Povidone iodine, chlorhexidine, and peroxide-based treatments are frequently utilized as primary wound irrigation/cleaning agents. Traditional agents like gentian violet and hypochlorites are less frequently utilized. Fusidic acid, mupirocin, neomycin sulphate, and iodine (typically as cadexomer iodine) are creams and ointments that are intended for longer contact [27].

Electrospun Scaffolds: With the help of cutting-edge technology called electrospinning, thin fibers can be fabricated with diameters ranging from a few nanometers to less than a micron. An electric field influences a charged polymer solution as it is driven through a nozzle. The liquid droplet at the nozzle becomes charged and appropriately extended in a continuous jet when a sufficient voltage is reached between the metallic collector and the nozzle. The jet flies to the collector and dries out along the journey. Electrospun scaffolds are excellent as skin replacement materials because of their resemblance to native ECM, variable pore size, large surface area, and oxygen permeability. Additionally, natural polymers, biomaterial and different bioactive chemicals, nanoparticles, and wound healing drugs can be loaded to nanofibers. The production of electrospun nanofibrous membranes using a variety of natural and synthetic polymers, as well as blends including them, has been explored. Applications for antibiotic-loaded electrospun matrices are numerous. Metal oxide nanoparticles have antibacterial properties and can be put in electrospun matrices to promote angiogenesis by preventing infection [14].

Conclusion: This review article provides a comprehensive update on the advancements in the treatment of surgical wound healing. The integration of novel therapies, technologies, and personalized medicine approaches holds great promise for improving wound healing outcomes, reducing complications, and enhancing patient well-being. However,

further research, clinical trials, and regulatory considerations are necessary to fully harness the potential of these innovative strategies in routine surgical practice.

Future perspectives: The field of surgical wound healing is poised for significant advancements in the coming years, driven by ongoing research and technological innovation. This section explores the future perspectives in the treatment of surgical wound healing, highlighting the exciting developments and potential directions that hold promise for improving patient outcomes. Regenerative medicine approaches, such as tissue engineering and stem cell therapies, show great potential for revolutionizing surgical wound healing. In the future, we can anticipate the development of advanced scaffolds and biocompatible materials that resembles the extracellular matrix, promoting the regeneration of functional tissues. The use of patient-specific stem cells or induced pluripotent stem cells may enable the creation of personalized therapies, accelerating wound healing and reducing complications.

Advanced Drug Delivery Systems: The development of innovative drug delivery systems will play a crucial role in optimizing surgical wound healing. The emergence of localized and controlled release systems, such as nanoscale drug carriers and hydrogels, capable of delivering therapeutic agents at precise locations and time points. These systems may facilitate targeted drug delivery, enhance bioavailability, and promote tissue regeneration, while minimizing systemic side effects.

Bioactive Dressings and Scaffolds: Future wound dressings and scaffolds are likely to incorporate bioactive components that actively participate in wound healing processes. These advanced materials may release growth factors, antimicrobial agents, and signaling molecules to modulate inflammation, promote angiogenesis, and accelerate tissue repair. Integration of sensors within dressings may enable real-time monitoring of wound parameters, allowing for personalized wound care and early detection of complications.

Precision Medicine Approaches: Advancements in molecular profiling techniques and genetic testing will enable personalized wound care based on individual patient characteristics. In the future, precision medicine approaches may guide treatment decisions by identifying genetic markers associated with wound healing outcomes, predicting patient response to specific therapies, and tailoring interventions accordingly. This personalized approach may lead to improved treatment outcomes and reduced healthcare costs.

Patient Engagement and Self-Management: There will be a greater emphasis on patient engagement and self-management in surgical wound healing. Mobile applications, wearable devices, and telemedicine solutions will empower patients to actively participate in their own care. These tools may provide personalized wound care instructions, track healing progress, and facilitate remote consultations with healthcare providers. By promoting patient education and self-monitoring, future interventions may lead to improved adherence, faster recovery, and reduced healthcare utilization.

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